
Interoperable solutions for implementing holistic **FLEXi**bility
services in the distribution **GRID**

Visual Materials and Identity Set – M18

Deliverable 9.6

WP9

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Approvals

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ABBREVIATIONS

PC: Project Coordinator

CA: Consortium Agreement

CC: Communication Committee

DoA: Description of Action

EC: European Commission

GA: General Assembly

IPR: Intellectual Property Right

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

M: Month

PH: Project Handbook

R&D: Research and Development

SC: Steering Committee

TP: Technical Partner

WP: Work Package

SME: Small and Medium Enterprise

DMP: Data Management Plan

H2020: Horizon 2020

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	6
2. VISUAL IDENTITY	7
2.1. Logotype Size.....	7
2.2. Logotype colour version.....	7
2.3. Logotype black & white (positive and negative) versions.....	8
2.4. Fonts.....	8
3. BRAND IDENTITY	9
3.1. Officials templates.....	9
3.1.1. Poster	9
3.1.2. Minutes Template	9
3.1.3. Agenda Template	9
3.1.4. List of attendees.....	10
3.1.5. Roll-up	10
3.1.6. General Presentation	12
3.1.7. Office Material	13
3.2. Events Materials.....	13
3.3. Merchandising.....	14
4. Workshop online materials	15
4.1 Avatar	15
4.2 Interaction	15
4.3 Event stage	16
4.4 Streaming and record.....	17
4.5 Text and imagen for social networks	17
5. Rules for including the consortium logos.....	18
6. Conclusions	19

1. INTRODUCTION

This manual serves as a guide for the identification and visual communication of FLEXI:GRID.

It includes the identity of the brand, the versions, colours, fonts and applications that should not vary in any case.

It is recommended to always use the high-quality version for printed documents and the screen version for digital documents.

Also shown are materials that can be made in the future. Some of the materials shown are examples and will be adapted according to the objectives and the context in which they are to be used.

2. VISUAL IDENTITY

2.1. Logotype Size

2cm

If the logo does not include the caption, it can be included up to a minimum of 2 centimetres wide to ensure its correct display, and the height will be proportional.

4,5cm

If the logo does not include the caption, it can be included up to a minimum of 4,5 centimetres wide to ensure its correct display, and the height will be proportional.

2.2. Logotype colour version

Below are shown the colours defined for the brand and the percentages and codes for the different variations of graphical reproductions.

CMYK 49 29 0 43
RGB 74 103 145
HEX #4A6791

CMYK 0 0 0 100
RGB 0 0 0
HEX #000000

CMYK 2 1 0 30
RGB 175 176 178
HEX #AFB0B2

CMYK 0 0 0 12
RGB 224 224 224
HEX #E0E0E0

2.3. Logotype black & white (positive and negative) versions

The brand may be used mainly in four colours. For those applications where it is not possible to use four-colours, other options in black & white one ink have been defined.

2.4. Fonts

The following font has been used to build the brand: NORWEST

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890

3. BRAND IDENTITY

3.1. Officials templates

3.1.1. Poster

Reproduction Poster in mock-up. Real size A1

Figure 1. Real poster of FLEXIGRID in an exhibition mock-up event

3.1.2. Minutes Template

Reproduction minutes template for FLEXIGRID meetings in mockup

Figure 2. Real minutes templates of FLEXIGRID in a page mock-up

3.1.3. Agenda Template

Reproduction agenda template for FLEXIGRID events in mockup

Figure 3. Real agenda template of FLEXIGRID in a page mock-up

3.1.4. List of attendees

Reproduction list attendees in FLEXIGRID events in mockup

Figure 4. Real list of attendees' list template of FLEXIGRID in a page mock-up

3.1.5. Roll-up

Roll-up design for events

Figure 5. Real roll-up of FLEXIGRID in a mock-up

3.1.6. General Presentation

General presentation of the project and template for presentations within the framework of the FLEXIGRID project

Figure 6. Real cover presentation of FLEXIGRID in a computer mock-up

The presentation consists of 12 slides:

- Slide 1:** FLEXIGRID logo and project title.
- Slide 2:** Info. about FLEXIGRID project. Includes budget (8.541.073,00€), duration (48 months), and coordinator (CIRCE).
- Slide 3:** FLEXIGRID - Project Objectives.
- Slide 4:** FLEXIGRID - Project Objectives. Main goal: to allow the distribution grid to operate in a secure and stable manner.
- Slide 5:** FLEXIGRID - Project Objectives. FLEXIGRID Specific Goals (Goal 1-4).
- Slide 6:** FLEXIGRID - Project Objectives. FLEXIGRID Specific Goals (Goal 5-8).
- Slide 7:** FLEXIGRID - Solutions, use cases & Demo sites.
- Slide 8:** FLEXIGRID - Solutions. Grid solutions for secondary substation, energy flow, and congestion management.
- Slide 9:** FLEXIGRID - Solutions. Architecture diagram showing the integration of various components.
- Slide 10:** FLEXIGRID - Use Cases & Demo Sites. Demo No. 1 - SPAIN. UC 1: Secondary substation; UC 2: Secondary substation with high RES penetration.
- Slide 11:** FLEXIGRID - Use Cases & Demo Sites. Demo No. 2 - GREECE. UC 3: Policy energy system; UC 4: Integrated congestion management and peak shaving.
- Slide 12:** FLEXIGRID - Use Cases & Demo Sites. Demo No. 3 - CROATIA. UC 5: Coordinating distribution systems; UC 6: Virtual energy storage for urban heating.

Figure 7. Real slides from the presentation of FLEXIGRID project

3.1.7. Office Material

Example of office equipment that could be produced during project implementation if deemed necessary for the project's dissemination activity

Figure 8. Example of office material of FLEXIGIRD project

3.2. Events Materials

During the project, an information brochure will be produced to disseminate the objectives and results of the project at events and meetings, as well as a roll-up to decorate stages, stands or any other place where FLEXIGRID.

The reproduction of badges has been made as an example of corporate material for events.

Figure 9. Example of staff or attendees' cards of FLEXIGIRD project

3.3. Merchandising

During the four years of the project different merchandising and image materials will be made. As an example, folders and mugs have been reproduced. These materials will be defined throughout the project according to the context in which they will be used.

Figure 10. Example of folder of FLEXIGIRD project

Figure 10. Example of merchandising material of FLEXIGIRD project

4. Workshop online materials

The first workshop with stakeholders and European Commission participation was held virtually on March 26, 2021, due to the pandemic situation.

To make the event more attractive, a company to provide a virtual stage was selected and networking space to allow interaction between the attendees.

4.1 Avatar

All attendees had the possibility to personalise their avatar to access the virtual platform.

Figure 11. Avatar customization screen

4.2 Interaction

The platform allowed for easy interaction with elements of the virtual stage such as sitting and accessing rooms. In addition, a real world was simulated. The avatar could approach other avatars and have a voice conversation. Also, during lectures, the avatar was able to clap its hands or raise its hand to ask questions in real time.

Figure 12. Interaction with the avatar with the elements of the platform (chairs, room...) and with other users.

Figure 13. Possibility of interacting with other users through voice simulating real life

4.3 Event stage

Two roles within the platform were possible: speaker and only attendee.

The speakers had the possibility to go on stage, share their presentation for viewing on the big screen for all attendees and, at the same time, the speaker could view it on a lectern.

Figure 14. Lectern with screen and presentation for the avatar making the presentation

Figure 15. View of the stage and screen from an attendee avatar as an audience

4.4 Streaming and record

To overcome connection problems, in addition to accessing the event via the virtual platform, it was possible to attend, and even participate, from an external application, via streaming.

The event was recorded and can be viewed at this [link](#)

4.5 Text and imagen for social networks

CIRCE, as WP9 coordinator, provided a text and several images to all project partners for the dissemination of the event.

You won't want to miss this #VirtualEvent of the #FLEXIGRIDproject!

The increasing share of variable and unpredictable renewable energy sources (RES) is challenging the electric grid in terms of reliability, stability and security of supply.

As an answer to these present and incoming challenges, FLEXI:GRID project proposes to improve the distribution grid operation making it more flexible, reliable and cost-efficient.

Within the framework of this European project, an innovative 3D event will be held to discuss all this through a platform that will allow you to interact with the space and the people around you as if it were a face-to-face event.

26 March
 9 a.m. to 1 p.m.
 Conference room
 Networking space

Don't miss it!
 Register here (mandatory): <https://lnkd.in/ds2zh8i>

See an example of the #VirtualSpaces and the agenda

[Ver traducción](#)

Figure 16. View of the stage and screen from an attendee avatar as an audience

5. Rules for including the consortium logos

Partners' logos should always be included in FLEXIGRID's official documents and graphics according to the following rules:

- Posters: must be included at the end of the design.
- Brochures or flyers or printed documents: may be included on the front or back cover, depending on the design.
- Power Point presentations or similar: to be included on the first or last slide.

Other documents which may include, but are not required to include

- Official document templates (agenda, minutes, list of attendees, etc): to include them, a specific cover should be made with the title of the document, in the context in which it is made and the set of logos. It will never go in the footer. The footer is reserved for the Acknowledgment of EU funding and Disclaimer.
- Merchandising materials (folders, event materials, objects, etc): may be included provided that adequate visibility is ensured.

6. Conclusions

This document contains ideas for materials to be used during the communication and dissemination actions to be carried out during the four years of project execution.

Some of the materials may vary in appearance with respect to those inserted as images depending on their scope and time of application.

In this M18 update the deliverable has no significant changes due to the global pandemic situation. Most of the actions have been in online format and it was not possible to deliver or visualize the materials.

The workshop held in March with project stakeholders and the participation of the European Commission through the virtual platform is the highlight of this deliverable. Due to pandemic times, the event was adapted to make its format and message more attractive so that a higher engagement could be achieved.